

**LABOR COURAGE OF WOMEN AND GIRLS IN UZBEKISTAN
DURING THE SECOND WORLD WAR**

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Annotation: The article covers significant facts about labor courage of women and girls in Uzbekistan during the second world war. In addition to this, in the article the life of women who lived in this period were noted as an example of this theme.

Key words: *multinational people, human spirit, wartime conditions, ideological pressure, women's activity, fascist women's, social producing, military section.*

As we know from history lessons, during the harsh years of war, all the people of Uzbekistan worked tirelessly with a single goal: "Everything for the front, everything for victory!". Our country turned into a reliable rear to supply the front. Uzbekistan produced and supplied the front with a large amount of military equipment and ammunition, food, clothing, medicines and other vital products. Thanks to the selfless labour of our multinational people, about 300 enterprises of the republic began to produce military products. Also, 151 factories were relocated from the frontline territories to Uzbekistan and put into operation in a short period of time. Thousands of wounded soldiers were treated in hospitals organized in our country. From the first months of the Great Patriotic War, all sectors of the national economy of Uzbekistan were rebuilt and directed towards military needs, including public education. Public education in Uzbekistan, including higher education institutions, went through severe trials. Most of the teaching staff and students were mobilized to the front. During the war of 1941-1945, the

role, prestige, influence and, most importantly, responsibility of a numerous group of intellectuals -teachers, who are the engineers of the human spirit, increased as never before. The workers of public education, in line with all the workers of the country, were able to make a worthy contribution to the fulfillment of all duties throughout the war time. Under wartime conditions, the development of public education was of great importance.

The public education authorities of Uzbekistan faced the difficult task of restructuring the work of its entire system, since during this difficult period the country needed highly qualified personnel more than ever. In addition to carrying out educational work in accordance with the requirements of the wartime period, representatives of the national education system intensified propaganda work among the population, which won them the respect of the people. During the crucial period of the war, hundreds of teachers were engaged in propaganda and agitation. With their direct participation, talks, collective listening to radio broadcasts and reading newspapers were organized throughout the country. In addition, reports, lectures and talks were given to the population. A large part of the public education workers were drafted into the ranks of the active army, and the remaining ones were entrusted with a number of difficult tasks at the same time. There were a lot of Uzbek women among the participants and heroes of World War II. During the soviet tyrant years Communist Party conducted policy in terms of women regarding their own purposes and trying to deal with this point under the ideological pressure led to severe consequences. Soviet Union and Communist Party had their own purpose that they intended to educate them as leader women who wanted to be interested in participating more actively in social and political life, not only caring for their own family. So some ideological and developing factors were organized for having an influence on women's activity. In World War II 1,5mln compatriots went into battlefield, at that time nearly 4 million people inhabited in our country. Four hundred thousand people died at war, about a

hundred thirty thousand people disappeared. That was a large loss for our population. During those years 4555 women from Uzbekistan fought in the battlefield at the same stage with men. In 1941 on 22nd of June that was the beginning of fight against fascist women's role increased the participation in national economy. They worked actively in each field of national economy, also instead of men who had gone to front. Millions of women showed their courage in labor as a response such mottos "Everything is for front!", "Everyone is for the protection of motherland", "as front in the back of the front!", "only forward and forward!", "do not leave without finishing the task![2]".

In community economy women's meetings with the initiative of women's departments were conducted and in districts conferences were carried out devoted to the duties of women at war. In 1943 on July and August in some cities and districts of Fergana region meeting was carried out devoted to women's role in social life at war. In October of that year in Fergana the meeting of associate workers from women's department was organized among provinces: over this province totally 20 538 women participated in meeting and conferences which were held in 1943 in August and September. In these meetings the working method and styles of women's departments were discussed and enlisting women to social producing were also discussed. Special places were organized for propaganda, women were informed about all news that was being happened in front and national economy[3].

One of them was Zebo Ganiyeva who was studying at Moscow Theatre Art Institute, after the beginning of war she did not want to come back her motherland, Andijan, she wanted to fight. That was the trace of the preference for courage and bravery. She became immediately master sniper and explorer. The military section that she was working was situated near the Moscow-Volga channel, the courage of that girl with greatcoat praised to the skies for the protection of Moscow. Her life was in danger several times, she participated 12 times "til" operation (to bring

catching alive captive in order to know the plans of enemy). The original name of Roza Nazirova was Xayriniso, she was born in Gortepa in 1904. After school graduation, she worked at MTC of Yangi yo'l of Tashkent province as a deputy of director, as a secretary in committee of former national economy party. She was rewarded with several medals acquiring attention her diligence, hard working. In previous days of war Roza addressed to military asking to send her front and she fought for the protection at war.

Widespread involvement of local women in production was necessary, first of all, to strengthen the economic base of the dictatorial regime. First of all, the main goal of socialism was to develop its economy, and for this purpose it used women as a labor force and involved them in social production. "In no country in the world except the socialist countries has the percentage of working women been so high". No one was interested in the natural subtlety of the female body, its inability to perform heavy physical labor, and the serious social consequences if this balance was disturbed. This was because the dictatorial regime was interested in their participation in production more than the family, emphasizing that their full freedom could not be ensured without the mass participation of women in production. Therefore, it was considered that "Economic independence is a key achievement in ensuring women's equality in society", "the main task in ensuring economic independence is to involve women in social work" [4].

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that in wartime conditions, a large number of young people had to go into production, therefore, covering them with training was an important state task. In 1941-1944, a large number of young people had to go to production. In 1941-1944, schools for working and village youth were opened in all cities and district centre, settlements, at large industrial enterprises, as well as in collective and state farms of the republic. It should also be noted that teachers play an important role in the development of public education, but in wartime conditions the problem of teacher personnel became acute, as

the main contingent of teachers were sent to the front, which contributed to a sharp decline in their number. For example, if in the 1940-1941 academic year the number of teachers in Uzbekistan was 36267, in the 1942-1943 academic year it was 30616. During the war years, the number of teachers in Uzbekistan decreased by 12,000. 357 schools in the republic suspended their activities due to staff shortages. In 1942, 2969 out of 5299 graduates of pedagogical institutes were sent to schools. And the rest were drafted into the army. Before the war only 33.4 per cent of teachers were women, during the war this figure increased to 55.3 per cent. In all branches of production and public education women became the main labour force.

REFERENCES:

1. Shamsutdinov R. Karimov Sh. History of motherland. - Tashkent: "Sharq", 2010. Page 356
2. Dilfuza Tukhtasinovna Sobirova, Farkhod Khasan ugli Abdullaev. The Contribution of Uzbek Women to the Victory in Second World War. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations. May 31, 2021
3. Sobirova D. History from women's in Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: "Akademnashr", 2014. Page 4